

21GRD10 QuantiAGREMI

D4: Summary report on the identified key-indicators and the improved emission models for increasing the representativeness of the emission estimations and determine their uncertainty. The report will also include the developed farm-monitoring systems for evaluating the efficiency of reduction measures, as well as the relevant farmers' management tools.

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1 Report on results of the campaigns, task 2.3.8 (VTT)- Deliverable D4

The aim of the work package (WP 2) is to contribute to the development of new sensors and measurement techniques for better estimation of livestock emissions. Deployment of these novel sensors and techniques will enable routine measurements for enforcement of emission policies and improve the expanse and quality of measurement data in inventories. Inside farm buildings, the conditions are challenging for these innovations.

Inside farm buildings, the conditions are challenging for these innovations. The presence of animals, their effluents and their feed create high moisture and dust levels, which are often not compatible with low-cost sensors that are being explored for continuous monitoring. In addition, the air composition in animal houses, and the related emission of gases, not only depends on the manure handling, the method of heating and on the type of feed, but is also time and place dependent, due to the differences in ventilation (chosen technique and speed) and animal type between different barns and farms. This challenges the development of novel uniform emission evaluation techniques. To cope with these complex conditions, there is a need for specially designed sensors, in different price categories with different levels of performance and capabilities, and new measurement approaches that provide more insight into the spatial and temporal variation of the air composition. This work package therefore focuses on a promising selection of novel sensors and measurement approaches

The sensors developed in Task 2.1 and other state-of-the-art sensors were evaluated in Task 2.2 to validate and improve their characteristics for field use.

As stated in A2.3.8:

- Using input from A2.3.3-A2.3.7, VTT, VSL, LUKE, WR, TNO, INRAE and IMTelecom will write a summary report based on the identified key-indicators and the improved emission models for increasing the representativeness of the emission estimations and determine their uncertainty. The report will also include the developed farm-monitoring systems for evaluating the efficiency of reduction measures, as well as the relevant farmers' management tools.

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3 Results from the field measurement campaigns performed in dairy farm in Finland (A2.3.3, A2.3.4) (VTT, LUKE)

The aim of task A2.3 was to assess the performance and applicability of the sensors and methods tested in Task 2.2. It is important to test the sensors and compare their operation in different conditions to extend the application field maximally.

In addition to the above-mentioned objective, which is stated in the project application, it was decided that the emissions of the barn (as mg/h) will be evaluated. The aim is to compare these calculations with the carbon balance method. Therefore, the velocities from all outlet channels of the building were measured during summer and winter measurement campaigns in Finland.

Summer campaign (A2.3.3) was performed during 13.8.-23.9.2024 and winter campaign (A2.3.4) 13.1.-27.2.2025.

Reference measurements were performed three times during the summer measurement campaign and two times during the winter campaign.

3.1 Information on the dairy barn, Finland

Natural Resources Institute Finland, LUKE, has dairy research barn located in Minkiö, Jokioinen, Finland (60.85546891110487, 23.47448957485535) with the capacity of 129 dairy cows. The barn has a closed system and is mechanically ventilated. The manure collection system is based on a slatted floor and natural gravity collection ending up in the slurry tanks. To provide a better quality air in the barn, a separate ventilation system aspirates the air under the slatted floor expected to have higher odor due to ammonia and other gases produced from manure fermentation herein called Slurry Ventilation. The barn was built to be based on a closed system, i.e., all the inlet and outlet air channels are controlled depending on the climatic condition.

The Barn building is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Dairy research barn, LUKE, Finland

3.2 Description of set-up at field measurement campaigns

General scheme of the measurement set-up is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Scheme for the measurement set-up

Unheated sampling lines (material polyethylene) were placed up to the channels, and the samples were sucked with the diaphragm pump with Teflon coating down to the sampling boxes where the sensors were sampling the same gas, therefore, making it possible to compare the results.

Sampling boxes are “flow through” set-ups where sample gas is sucked using pump. These sampling boxes were flushed with fresh air thoroughly before the measurements. Filters were used in the beginning of each sampling line to remove particles. Filters were changed over time to ensure air flow to the lines.

3.3 Flow measurements

Air flow was measured at the beginning of the measurement campaign from each outlet-channel with hot wire anemometer (model: EE650), performing discontinuous grid measurement. The aim of this measurement was to know the air flow from each outlet channel.

Barn personnel operated the fans manually during the measurement campaign. It was agreed with them that they will keep the fans running at constant speed during the measurement campaign.

Continuous flow measurement (with hot-wire anemometer) was performed from one outlet channel (where the concentration measurements are also performed) and the data from these measurements was stored into data logging system (during summer campaign, 21.8.-23.9.2024 and during winter campaign, 30.1.-27.2.2025).

Air flow of inlet channels was not measured since the ventilation rate is assumed to be equal to the outlet in a closed barn and due to practical difficulties.

Examples of outlet and inlet channels inside the barn are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example of outlet ventilation channel inside the barn and view to the barn, vertical channel with inlet ventilation ports (yellow pipeline)

3.4 Reference analysers

Reference analysers that were used in these campaigns were based on following technologies:

- FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared)
- OFCEAS (Optical Feedback Cavity Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy)
- CRDS (Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy)

These analysers, as well as a general view on the measurement set-up, are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Reference analysers, and view on the measurement set-up, used in quantiAGREMI field campaigns, LUKE barn, Finland.

3.4.1 FTIR analyser

Performance of the Gasetm Dx4000 FTIR analyser was tested at VTT using SI-traceable calibration gases. VTT used SI-traceable calibration gases which were used to produce reference spectra (with several concentration ranges) for following components:

- CO₂ 10,000 ppm in nitrogen, expanded uncertainty 0.75 %, manufacturer: Air Products
- CH₄ 3,000 ppm in nitrogen, expanded uncertainty 1 %, manufacturer: Air Products
- N₂O 100 ppm in nitrogen, expanded uncertainty 1.5 %, manufacturer: Air Products
- NH₃ 100 ppm in nitrogen, expanded uncertainty 2 %, manufacturer: Linde
- Nitrogen (IR inactive gas) is used as zero gas.

Tests for FTIR analyser (for which VTT has accreditation according to EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017, accreditation code T259) were performed according to the principles of Technical Specification, produced by CEN/TC264, CEN/TS 17337 “Stationary source emissions. Determination of mass concentration of multiple gaseous species. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy”.

3.4.2 OFCEAS analyser

The manufacturer (AP2E) of the OFCEAS analyser performed the calibration prior to shipping the rental unit to VTT. VTT performed analyser calibration check at laboratory conditions for CH₄ using static reference gas mixture cylinder from A1.1.5 and with the dynamic reference gas generator from A1.1.4 to produce RGM in synthetic air or nitrogen for humid NH₃ and H₂O. During the field measurements, the performance of the

analyser was tested with SI traceable calibration gases from 3.1.4 and the reference gas generator. The specified measurement range and limit of detection (LOD) are:

- CH₄ 0 – 1000 ppm, LOD 0.7 ppm
- NH₃ 0 – 1500 ppm, LOD 0.2 ppm
- N₂O 0 – 250 ppm, LOD 0.01 ppm

3.4.3 CRDS analyser

The performance of the Picarro G2204 CRDS analyser for CH₄ was tested in laboratory conditions using static reference gas mixture cylinder from A1.1.5. In field conditions, the performance of the analyser was tested with SI traceable calibration gases from 3.4.1. The specified measurement range and precision are:

- CH₄ 0 – 20 ppm, precision 1% of reading

3.5 Tested sensors

3.5.1 Senseair

Senseair provided a prototype of a compact high-resolution multi-channel NDIR sensor that is still under development. Named K96 (Figure 5), the sensor can be configured to measure simultaneously either CH₄ or N₂O in combination with H₂O and CO₂ with 800 ms measurement interval (Figure 6). Active sampling (0.7-1 L/min) and data logging capability were deployed during the campaign for field evaluation.

Figure 5. Senseair K96 multi-channel NDIR sensor (dim: 4*3*3 cm) **Figure 6.** K96 integrated devices

The K96 sensors are individually calibrated by Senseair to report mole fractions in the following ranges:

- CH₄: 0- 3,200 ppm with 0.1 ppm resolution
- N₂O: 0- 3,200 ppm with 0.1 ppm resolution
- H₂O: 0- 32,000 ppm with 1 ppm resolution
- CO₂: 0- 32,000 ppm with 1 ppm resolution

The K96 prototype introduces multi-gas capability as a key feature to compensate for cross-sensitivities between NDIR channels. It is for instance known that the CH_4 measurement is affected by the H_2O content in the air sample, while the N_2O measurement suffers from interferences with CO_2 and H_2O . These cross-sensitivities are, as of today, not compensated automatically in the K96. Senseair has worked on establishing correction methods that were evaluated during the project.

Senseair provided also a prototype of NH_3 & CO_2 sensor (Figure 7) which is a customized version of a commercial alcohol in breath sensor¹. Two units were deployed on 29.8.2024, one placed in the outbox of the slurry box and the other in the outbox of the outlet channel. These NH_3 sensors were individually calibrated by Senseair to report NH_3 and CO_2 in the following ranges: 0-3,200 ppm (0.1 ppm resolution) for NH_3 and 0-64,000 ppm (2 ppm resolution) for CO_2 . The sensors have active sampling (using a fan) but are not equipped with an inlet port for easy connection with a sample line. The NH_3 sensors do not provide data logging capability and were deployed with single board PCs for data acquisition.

Figure 7. NH_3 -sensors by Senseair

3.5.2 Gasera prototype instrument

Gasera provided one prototype instrument for simultaneous measurements of CH_4 - N_2O - NH_3 - H_2O concentrations. The sensor is equipped with one QCL light source near 1195 cm^{-1} ($8.37 \mu\text{m}$) which is periodically tuned to features of each target gas during a measurement cycle. Sample interval, or the measurement cycle, of the instrument is approx. 53 seconds. The instrument has an internal pump, which has a flow rate of $\sim 1 \text{ L/min}$ during the gas exchange cycle, which lasts for approx. 5 seconds at the start of each measurement cycle. The unit can be controlled via graphical UI, and the measurement data along with many

¹ <https://senseair.com/product/senseair-a-one/>

other parameters is automatically logged. A rendered image of the unit is shown in Figure 8. The instrument is housed in 19" rack.

Concentration ranges for these target gases are:

- NH_3 : 0-100 ppm
- CH_4 : 0-100 ppm
- N_2O : 0-100 ppm
- H_2O : 0-30,000 ppm

Figure 8. Gasera prototype analyser

3.5.3 Vaisala

Vaisala provided several CO_2 , humidity and temperature sensors (5 units) for both summer and winter measurement campaigns (an example is shown in Figure 9).

- 5 x GMP252 Carbon Dioxide Probe, range: 0-2,000 ppm
- 4 x HMP7 Humidity and Temperature Probe, 0- 100 %rh, -40 °C- +180 °C
- 1 x HMP9 Humidity and Temperature Probe, 0- 100 %rh, -40 °C- +120 °C
- 5 x Indigo520 transmitters
- In-situ measurements, no pumps

Data was logged in 10 min intervals. The data includes min, max and average values during this time.

The devices were initially factory calibrated, and between the measurement campaigns, ISO 17025 accredited calibrations were performed for each instrument.

Figure 9. Vaisala Indigo host with CO₂, humidity and temperature probes

3.5.4 IMTelecom

Field comparison tests in Finland could not include the AMON sensors developed by IMTelecom, as their detection range was not suitable.

It should be recalled that the AMON sensors are designed for the monitoring of ambient ammonia concentrations, typically expected to remain below 500 ppb. A dedicated development effort was nonetheless initiated in order to extend the detection range by intentionally reducing the sensor's sensitivity.

However, the data acquisition system associated with the AMON sensor prevented these measurements from being performed.

This limitation ultimately prompted a redesign of the acquisition electronics to overcome range constraints, through the implementation of a dual conversion process (resistance-to-frequency, followed by frequency-to-voltage conversion).

3.6 Results

3.6.1 Velocity measurements

Velocities were measured twice discontinuously during the summer campaign from all seven outlet channels (on 14.8. and on 18.9.) and continuously from the same channel where the concentration measurements were performed, channel nr 2. Slurry pit channels (3 pieces) were measured on 15.8.2024.

The flow from the barn is calculated by multiplying measured velocities (m/s) with the area of the channel ($A=\pi r^2$ (m²)), thus giving the flow as m³/h.

On the first day, 14.8.2024, flow was on average 49,600 Nm³/h from the outlet channels and on 15.8. 670 m³/h on average from the slurry pit channels. The portion of the air from slurry pit channels is thus 1.3 % of the total flow, and it can be considered negligible.

The flow measured on 18.9.2024 from all seven outlet channels was on average 52,700 Nm³/h, meaning that it was about 3,000 Nm³/h larger than during previous measurements on 14.8.2024 when standardizing from m³/h in Nm³/h (2% difference when not standardizing).

Unfortunately, the barn has no information on the ventilation rates or the flow (as m³/h), so the measured values could not be compared with this information.

Results of the continuous flow measurement with hot-wire anemometer are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Continuous flow measurement as m/s from outlet channel nr 2 during summer campaign

Grey and orange dots show the spot measurements that were performed at the beginning and at the end of the measurement campaign by Pitot-tube and hot-wire anemometer. As can be seen from the Figure 10, there is a declining trend in continuous flow measurement. This is most probably due to the dirt that has been collected on the surface of the hot-wire anemometer, causing a decrease in the sensitivity of the anemometer.

During winter measurements, continuous velocity measurement was started on 30.1.2025. Spot measurements from each outlet channel were performed on 30.1.2025 and on 26.2.2025. During the measurements performed on 30.1.2025, it was noticed that the fans in outlet channels nr 2, 4 and 6 were not operating, only outlet channel fans 1, 3, 5 and 7 were on, and the rest were off. Therefore, flows during winter measurements were less stable than during the summer period. Instability of flow in channel 2 used for air sampling to “outbox” can explain instability of concentrations including very low concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄. As a matter of fact, when the ventilator stops, the channel 2 can serve as an inlet when cold outside air entries due to gravity and wind effect. Therefore, during these periods, outside air can be pumped to “outbox” and replace partly or totally inside air depending on duration of zero-ventilation and pumping rate. Then, when the ventilator restarts, only inside air is pumped to “outbox” and it recovers better stability in concentrations.

Results of the continuous flow measurement with hot-wire anemometer are shown in Figure 11. Note! Due to malfunction of the data storage, data is available only from 13.-27.2.2025. Total ventilation was 81% of summer ventilation when all ventilators were running (42700 Nm³/h). Standard deviation of hot-wire anemometer observations during one week without drift was 0.25 m/s (4.4%) in winter and 0.16 m/s (1.8%) in summer.

Figure 11. Continuous flow measurement as m/s from outlet channel nr 2 during winter campaign

3.6.2 Sensor comparison with reference analysers

3.6.2.1 Measurements with reference gases

Reference gases were fed to the sample boxes and concentrations were measured with sensors and reference instruments. Concentrations were:

- 2 ppm and 20 ppm N₂O
- 100 ppm and 200 ppm CH₄
- 9.1 ppm and 10.1 ppm NH₃ (wet)
- 1000 ppm and 2000 ppm CO₂

Concentrations were measured with reference analysers (FTIR, CRDS and OFCEAS) and with sensors, and the results are shown in Figure 12- Figure 14. Reference analysers are marked in Figures as “VTT-AP2E”,

“VTT-FTIR” and “VTT-Picarro”. Note! Sensors with the abbreviation “WR” refer to Axetris for CH₄, Dräger for NH₃ and Vaisala for CO₂.

Figure 12. (a & b). Summary of INBOX measurements with different sensors and reference analysers (AP2E, Picarro and FTIR)

In Figure 12 a, we can see that Gasera prototype gave 14.9 ppm result for 10.1 ppm NH₃ concentration. However, the calibration that was performed at PTB after this summer campaign revealed that the readings had to be corrected by a factor of 1/1.51. This would mean that the 14.9 ppm reading would be 9.87 ppm. The error was caused by Gasera’s factory calibration which needs to be adjusted.

The reading for Senseair CH₄ sensor to 200 ppm CH₄ reference gas was 192 ppm in the summer campaign. During winter campaign, 100 ppm CH₄ gas was fed to sample box, and Senseair CH₄ sensor’s response was varying, being first 129 ppm and later on 77 ppm. This was due to the sensor drift.

Both Senseair and Gasera show good agreement with N₂O reference gas. Also, Senseair CO₂ sensors had good agreement with the CO₂ reference gas.

Sensors sent by WR to these campaigns (Dräger, Axetris and Vaisala) were calibrated before campaigns at the laboratory of WR. As can be seen from all these Figures 12-14, there is good agreement with reference gases and these results. It must be noted that these sensors are commercially available products, not prototypes.

Figure 13. (a & b). Summary of OUTBOX measurements with different sensors and reference analysers (AP2E, Picarro and FTIR)

Senseair sensor show good agreement with N₂O reference gas on high concentration (20 ppm N₂O). For low N₂O concentration there is an offset. Senseair CO₂ sensors had good agreement with the CO₂ reference gas. There is an offset in the readings of Senseair CH₄ sensor, as well as in Senseair NH₃ sensor., between summer and winter campaigns. Different sensors were used to measure in/out/slurry air samples between summer and winter campaigns. In addition, different calibration gas mixtures were used between summer and winter

campaigns. These tests show that the cross-sensitivity management for Senseair sensors needs further improvement.

Gasera prototype analyser shows good agreement with N₂O reference gas on low concentration (2 ppm N₂O) and for CH₄ reference gas (100 ppm).

Figure 14. (a & b). Summary of SLURRYBOX measurements with different sensors and reference analysers (AP2E, Picarro and FTIR)

Senseair sensor shows good agreement with N₂O reference gas both on high and low concentration (20 ppm and 2 ppm N₂O). Senseair CO₂ sensors had good agreement with the CO₂ reference gas, as well as Senseair NH₃ sensor had good agreement with the NH₃ reference gas (10.1 ppm NH₃).

3.6.2.2 Measurements from sample gas

Sample gas measurements, with sensors and simultaneously with reference instruments, from each sample boxes are given in figures 15-26 (a & b).

Figure 15. (a & b). CH₄ measured from sample gas in INBOX with Gasera, Senseair, Axetris (WR) and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (27.2.2025)

Figure 16. (a & b). N_2O measured from sample gas in INBOX with Senseair and Gasera and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (30.1.2025)

Figure 17. (a & b). NH_3 measured from sample gas in INBOX with Gasera and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (30.1.2025)

Figure 18. (a & b). CO_2 measured from sample gas in INBOX with Vaisala sensors (WR and Vaisala), Senseair and reference analysers (FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (27.2.2025)

Figure 19. (a & b). CH_4 measured from sample gas in OUTBOX with Senseair, Gasera, Axetris (WR) and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.-27.2.2025)

Figure 20. (a & b). N_2O measured from sample gas in OUTBOX with Senseair and Gasera and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.-27.2.2025)

Figure 21. (a & b). NH_3 measured from sample gas in OUTBOX with Senseair, Gasera, Dräger (WR) and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.-27.2.2025).

Figure 22. (a & b). CO_2 measured from sample gas in OUTBOX with Vaisala sensors (WR and Vaisala), Senseair and reference analysers (FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.-27.2.2025)

Figure 23. (a & b). CH_4 measured from sample gas in SLURRYBOX with Senseair, Gasera, Axetris (WR) and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.2.2025)

Figure 24. (a & b). N_2O measured from sample gas in SLURRYBOX with Senseair, Gasera and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.2.2025)

Figure 25. (a & b). NH_3 measured from sample gas in SLURRYBOX with Senseair, Gasera, Dräger (WR) and reference analysers (AP2E and FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.2.2025)

Figure 26. (a & b). CO_2 measured from sample gas in SLURRYBOX with different Senseair sensors, Vaisala (WR) and reference analysers (FTIR), summer (19.9.2024) and winter results (26.2.2025).

3.6.2.3 Temporal variations

Temporal variations during summer and winter campaigns, measured from OUTBOX are presented below in Figures 27-30.

Figure 27. CO_2 temporal variations measured with sensors during summer and winter campaigns, outbox

Figure 28. CH₄ temporal variations measured with sensors during summer and winter campaigns, outbox

Figure 29. NH₃ temporal variations measured with sensors during summer and winter campaigns, outbox

Figure 30. N₂O temporal variations measured with sensors during summer and winter campaigns, outbox

3.6.3 Comparison of CO₂ emissions

Following methods were implemented during the Finnish campaign:

- emission deduced from ventilation and concentrations measured with calibrated sensors (1);

- emission deduced from measured concentrations and modelled ventilation (CO₂ model from DIN 18910) (2);
- simplified method using CO₂ as internal tracer and a “farmer questionnaire” to estimated C losses (3).

The mass balance method could not be implemented. The house was not designed to collect the manure during the experimental period and assess its contribution to the budget. Therefore, it was not possible to assess the mass balance deficit of water, carbon and nitrogen during the Finnish field campaign. However, temporal variations shown in Figure 27 to Figure 29 indicate that the presence of animals in the housing is a critical data to measure emissions.

The CO₂ emission is the key variable used in all these methods (see deliverable D2). All methods should converge on the same emissions of NH₃, CH₄ and N₂O provided the CO₂ emission estimated by all methods is “true” and gas concentrations are correctly calibrated and measured on positions representative of inlet and outlet air.

Emission of CO₂ deduced from ventilation and concentrations measured with calibrated sensors (1) is based on CO₂ concentrations measured in boxes (In-box and out-box) and ventilation measured with air speed sensors presented above. In summer, it was 62.5 kg CO₂ / h for the house. From activity data (LUKE farm) the number of lactating cows was 96 and 10 dry cows. The contribution of less than 10 calves to total CO₂ production was neglected. It gives 589 g CO₂ / h /dairy cow ± 12, assuming that the value is true and a 2% standard uncertainty due to uncertainties in sensors, sampling representativity and activity data.

The average hourly CO₂ emission per cow estimated by DIN 18910 (2) depends on:

- liveweight (627 kg/cow ± 1),
- milk production (30.6 kg/day/cow ± 1),
- pregnancy (estimated 140 day/cow ± 30),
- ambient temperature (23.8 °C ± 1.5),
- CO₂ conversion factor (0.200 L CO₂ /h/W heat production ± 0.01 chosen according to values ranging between 0.17 and 0.20 for all animals
- assumed density of 1.81 g CO₂ / L CO₂).

We used a Monte-Carlo approach to estimate standard uncertainty due to these input data.

Concerning these variables, the “day” does not belong to SI (VIM, 2012). The other inputs can be traced with traceable instruments. The model indicates 514 ± 26 g CO₂ /h /dairy cow.

When replacing milk by “fat corrected milk” (FCM =0,4*Milk_kg+15*[Fat_gr per kg*Milk_kg/1000]) with the observed fat content (53.4 g FAT /kg milk ± 1), the CO₂ production becomes 564 ± 30 g CO₂ /h /dairy cow. Another model can be used (“energy corrected milk”, using fat and protein contents) to take into account the variable composition of milk. None of them is used in DIN 18910. Nevertheless, this norm has been set up to design the ventilation and thermal insulation of animal housings in winter and summer. Therefore, we consider that estimate of DIN 18910 agrees well with reference value. The model can induce a bias on emission estimates depending on knowledge on input data (liveweight, milk, pregnancy, temperature, manure contribution to CO₂ production of the house).

The simplified method (3) we used is based on estimates on inputs and outputs of carbon representing specifically the housing. It estimates total carbon losses from a questionnaire including previous inputs (liveweight, milk, fat and protein content of milk) and estimates of feed and litter input to the manure. The liveweight is used to check the consistency of feed input. Coefficients are used to estimate manure production and associated carbon losses. Measurements of CO₂ and CH₄ inside and outside the house are used to deduce the fractions of CH₄ and CO₂ in total carbon losses. All inputs and coefficients are SI-traceable as they are deduced from a mass balance. However, the trueness of the coefficients could be hardly verified as they

apply to commercial farms where these values are in most cases not recorded. In the current case, liveweight and production were accurately known (same data than for method 2), but not feed from grazing. Therefore, a default value of feed was chosen based on liveweight (3.2 ± 0.5 kg dry matter feed / 100 kg liveweight dairy cow). The CO₂ production was estimated 596 ± 80 g CO₂/h/dairy cow. When feed is not known, the uncertainty of CO₂ production is above 10%. This figure is true regarding the reference emission. The comparison with the estimate of DIN 18910 shows the importance of taking feed into account to reduce potential bias in CO₂ emission.

Method	CO ₂ emissions (g CO ₂ /h /dairy cow)
Ventilation and concentrations measured with calibrated sensors (2)	589 ± 12
Measured concentrations and modeled ventilation (CO ₂ model from DIN 18910)	564 ± 30
The simplified method (3)	596 ± 80

3.6.4 “Spatial representativeness” of concentration measurements

As shown on Figure 31 and discussed theoretically in A1.4.3, gas concentrations vary significantly depending on the sampling position while the spatial variability of concentrations varies with time. Continuous measurements are necessary to catch this variability while Figure 31 (a) shows that outside sensor should be corrected for bias. It also shows the importance of synchronized observations for adequate analysis and correct concentration gradients (indoor-outdoor) for time shift due to mixing delay of outside air. In the case of large barns and high number of animals, the concentrations outside, close to air inlets, depend on background concentrations but also on the gases that are released by the barn. Local air stability due to climate (small wind, radiative cooling, confined topography and vegetation around the house) reduce the dispersion of air released by ventilation.

Figure 31. Observed spatial variability of concentration measurements. (a) observations on August 20th show a calibration issue on outside sensor and the time lag between outside and inside concentrations (red line); (b) sample bags were collected by walking inside and outside the barn while in-box and out-box corresponded to air duct on the roof of the house: the CO₂ difference is higher when calculated from box measurements.

The concentrations inside the barn depend on the combination of three main processes:

- the heterogeneity of ventilation (more or less confined areas and associated dilution of emitted gases; also modelled with the concept of variable “age of air” inside the house),
- the movement of air (increase in concentrations when the air moves from one inlet to one outlet, e.g. the so-called “tunnel-ventilation” in poultry housings),
- the spatial heterogeneity of sources inducing a variable stoichiometry between the different gases (e.g. CO₂ emission depends on the position of animals that mainly depends on the feeding and resting behavior while NH₃ emission depends on the position where excretion is concentrated and accumulated).

All these processes depend on the barn, the climate, the animal behavior, the management practices of the farmer. The farmer adapts the management to changes in climate and animals in order to optimize his revenue. Therefore, improving the representativeness of emission measurements requires increasing the number of both activity data measurements and gas concentration measurements. The mass balance of carbon, nitrogen and water of the animal house remains the most cost-effective observation to evaluate the trueness of annual emissions (see uncertainty paragraph) as it is tightly connected to the specific efficiency of the production process on the farm.

3.6.5 Improvement of methods and models for monitoring emissions from animal housings regarding target applications

As accurate modelling of emission processes require several inputs, the “cost-effective” optimum of the protocol to measure the emissions in a given farm depends on the Target Application (see deliverable D2). From above observations and analyses, simple improvements of methods and models can be suggested to match the needs of the different Target Applications as well as the needs of a metrological infrastructure as presented in BIPM-OIML (2021).

The minimal requirement for measurements is to clarify the measurands, the measurement models and the uncertainty sources. When models are used (measurement models and models of animal productions), SI-traceable input variables should be preferred and indications should be given on the experimental conditions that can be used to calibrate parameters, ensure comparability of experiments in different countries and share results as FAIR datasets. To adapt the model to SI units, the “day” should be removed from the chosen variables. For example, the Petersen matrix formalism (yields of transformation) could be used to express the partition of feed into animal growth, milk production, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions and excretion. A comprehensive formalism should enhance comparability across monitoring studies. This formalism could be completed by the changes in stoichiometry (e.g. ratios of C, H, O, N, P, K, Ca, Cl to total non-volatile solids) from feed into milk, animal body, excretion, gases to have a comprehensive, comparable and SI-traceable description of the dataset. In case of checking stoichiometry in commercial farms, these ratios could serve as reference databases for default values (e.g. when a significant decrease in NH₃ emission [increase in CO₂:NH₃ emission ratio] from liquid manure is due to improved nitrogen conservation, then, a significant increase in the N:K ratio of liquid manure should be observed). As a matter of fact most farmers use hours, days, seasons and years for time units. However, if models are based on animal inputs and productions, the farmers and their advisors can easily adapt model outputs and uncertainties to appropriate time scales and to more or less intensive production rates. Moreover, increasing production rates (e.g. milk per day, growth per day, eggs per day) is in most cases correlated to quantity and composition of imported feed as well as duration of presence of animals (on-farm traceable information) even if it also depends on animal genetics, environment and farmer management that change over the years.

As shown in DIN 18910, all animal productions using animal housing are concerned with CO₂ emission and concentrations. This norm gives figures as a function of production but does not include feed information. Nevertheless, feed efficiency is a key component of farmers’ income and not homogeneous between farms. Moreover, nitrogen content of feed and nitrogen efficiency regarding animal production are key data to predict excreted nitrogen. Therefore, we suggest adding feed variable in next generations of models and estimates of nitrogen content, as well as their variability, to improve accuracy of model outputs and estimates of

uncertainties. The purpose is to improve the trueness of model predictions. but also the definition of the measurands (particularly for SI-traceable experiments with animals that cannot be accurately repeatable) and therefore the detection level of differences between periods where the animals were different but managed in the same way (e.g. CO₂ emission or emission factors from a cow weighing 650 kg, producing 8000 kg standard milk between 1st January and 31st December, producing in average 25 kg standard milk per 24h during the observed period).

The minimum requirement (Target Application TA4; “field monitoring”) is focusing on SI-traceable activity data and gas concentrations specific of the farm. For gas sampling, all the relevant areas inside the barn (e.g. here, in a dairy barn, the area where the lactating cows are feeding, resting and milking). If the number of measurements is limited, than the periods supposed to have the highest share in annual emission should be considered for sampling gas concentrations inside the barn to maximize representativeness of observations.

Then, for applications requiring a large number of farms (representativeness of “emission factor” to the category, TA1), attention should paid on the sampling of farms and periods and on the traceability of both activity data and gas concentrations. As both are critical in the measurement model, redundancy of collected data should be designed to allow quality checks and occasional data corrections.

For applications requiring the measurement of small differences (Target Application TA2), continuous measurements and simultaneous measurement of control and treatment (“mitigation techniques”) should be preferred, using SI-traceable instruments, including the redundancy required to evaluate the trueness of emissions and verify the spatial representativeness of concentration measurements or the homogeneity of gas concentrations. These experiments are expected to be expensive and have a higher environmental impact than the expected reduction in the monitored system. However, they can provide specific model calibrations that could be used in TA3 to evaluate the trueness of results in similar farms with a much lower cost and environmental impact (“testing the efficiency”).

3.7 Conclusions and observations from the Finnish field measurement campaigns (VTT, LUKE, Senseair, Gasera, Vaisala)

3.7.1 3.7.1 Sensors

During the field test campaigns in Finland, measurements were carried out in both summer and winter conditions using sensors and reference analysers. Following components were measured: NH₃, N₂O, CH₄ and CO₂.

Sensors/analysers tested were from Senseair and Gasera. Gasera provided a prototype analyser for these tests which was used in field measurement for the first time in this project.

Other instruments used in these field measurements are already commercially available products, including:

- Vaisala sensors for the measurement of CO₂, humidity and temperature
- Dräger for the measurement of NH₃
- Axetris for the measurement of CH₄

Comparative measurements between sensors and reference analysers were conducted in two ways:

1. Calibration gas with a known concentration was fed into sample boxes
 - In the summer measurements, the test gas contained only one gas and they were fed one by one to the sample boxes (20 ppm N₂O, 200 ppm CH₄ and 2000 ppm CO₂).

- In the winter measurements, however, a gas mixture was fed into the sample boxes where the sensors and analysers were sampling from. This allowed the investigation of possible effects of the gas matrix on sensor readings. The gas mixture contained 2 ppm N₂O, 100 ppm CH₄, and 1000 ppm CO₂.
 - Ammonia, on the other hand, was fed as a pure humid gas mixture (9.06 ppm NH₃ + 1 % H₂O)
2. After these measurements, sampling continued from normal sampling points (out, in and slurry), and the gas from the sample boxes was measured not only with sensors but also with reference analysers. This allowed for observation of whether real gas matrix affected sensor readings.

The importance of calibration of the sensors must be emphasized. For example, in Figure 12a we can see that Gasera prototype shows the reading of 14.9 ppm for the 10.1 ppm NH₃ calibration gas concentration in the summer campaign measurements. However, the calibration performed at PTB after summer tests revealed that Gasera readings had to be corrected by a factor of 1/1.51. This would mean that the 14.9 ppm reading would be 9.87 ppm. The error was caused by Gasera's factory calibration which needs to be adjusted.

When looking at Figures 15-26, there is a good agreement between the sensors and reference analysers. This can be said for all components, especially considering that the measured concentrations, especially for N₂O and NH₃ were low.

In addition, chapter 3 presents, for both summer and winter measurements, the concentrations measured by the sensors over the entire measurement periods (temporal variations).

For N₂O, a drift can be seen in the temporal variation results during summer campaign (Figure 30). During the test days with standard analysers, concentrations of CO₂, CH₄, NH₃ and N₂O measured from IN-box by all the sensors and analysers were similar during summer and winter campaigns despite having more variation for CH₄ and N₂O over days during summer compared to winter campaign (Figure 15-18). Concentrations of CO₂, CH₄, NH₃ and N₂O measured from OUT-box were higher for all the sensors and analysers during winter compared with summer campaign (Figure 19-22). This was mainly due to the lower ventilation rate during the winter campaign while the number of animals producing those gases remained rather constant. Unchanged concentrations of NH₃ and N₂O can be a joint result of lower ventilation rate and lower manure fermentation due to lower winter temperature in the barn. Manure fermentation is the main source of NH₃ and N₂O (with very low N₂O emissions from liquid manure). Similarly, concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄ from SLURRY-box were higher for all the sensors and analysers during winter compared with summer campaign (Figure 23 and 26) which can be explained by a higher number of animals in the building during the winter than in the summer. However, NH₃ and N₂O concentrations were not different (Figure 24 and 25).

During the whole campaign, concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄ from OUT-box were higher for all the sensors and analysers during winter compared with summer campaign (Figure 27 and 28) whereas NH₃ and N₂O concentrations remained within the same range (Figure 29 and 30). Daily variations with a repeated pattern in concentrations of CO₂, CH₄, NH₃ and N₂O were identified by the sensors during both winter and summer campaigns. Many daily routines, including paddock doors opening and closing, cleaning the manure with water pressure, working diesel machinery, feeding times etc. can contribute to the temporal variations observed. For instance, a feeder working with diesel was working every day between 9-11 AM which can explain why the Senseair sensors measured regular N₂O peaks during that period. Exhaust gases from the diesel engine likely contain CO which is known to interfere with the N₂O measurement in the K96 sensor. Another example is that CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations measured from Out-box during the summer campaign were responsive to the number of cows kept outside during the day for grazing and inside during the night (16.8.-12.09. and 18.-19.09.) indicating higher variation during day and night compared to other days when all the cows were kept inside the barn.

We conclude that low-cost devices are a viable solution for continuous monitoring of livestock emissions provided that traceable calibration is carried out. Some sensor manufacturers need to further improve their correction methods to reduce cross-interferences. Senseair K96 multi-gas sensor allows to correct for cross-sensitivities between interfering gases. Correction methods were tested during the project, showing promising results and opening ways for further improvements.

The quantiAGREMI project and its field measurements in Finland provided profound information to sensor manufacturers so that they can develop their products further to be used under farm condition.

3.7.2 Activity data to assess annual emissions of farms

During the field test campaigns in Finland, activity data was used to standardize housing emission (convert total house emission into dairy emission) and to estimate CO₂ emission (DIN 18910) or the carbon loss of the house (simplified method). Activity data can be SI-traceable when they refer to commercial activities. However, commercial activity is not sufficient to reflect accurately the production processes ongoing on the farm. For example, a part of the milk is not commercialized when dairy cows receive medicals or if it is transformed in the farm. Therefore, additional statistics, reflecting either the farm specificity or the farm category and its variability, would be useful to improve representativeness of model predictions when SI-traceable activity data is used as model inputs.

During the field test campaigns, the cows went grazing partly during the day, partly during the night or not during the winter period. When the cows went grazing, a part of the animals stayed in the house. This activity data has a high influence on the quantity of manure produced in the house and the corresponding emissions of NH₃, CH₄ and N₂O. Grazing belongs to the social demand. It is considered as a mitigation technique to reduce NH₃ emissions from housings. It also depends on climate and possibilities around the house. Therefore, improving the accuracy of this activity data is critical to improve the representativeness of annual emissions of farms.

In the case of cattle, important dates are recorded on animal scale in national databases (e.g. birth, death, calving). These SI-traceable data could be used by models based on interoperability rules and highly improve the estimates of minimal feed intake per animal that has a critical influence on modelled CO₂ and CH₄ emissions and on minimal nitrogen excretion.

3.7.3 Conversion of emission measurements in housing emissions per house or per category

Improvement of methods and models were suggested following the field campaign in Finland. Improving current measurand definitions, measurement models and models of animal production by using SI-traceable inputs could help proposing SI-traceable experiments to improve model calibration, improve comparability of experiments between countries and share FAIR datasets.

With improved models of animal production, improved description of uncertainty sources used in measurement models, use of traceable climate data and traceable sensors of concentration measurement should help increasing the representativeness (trueness) of emission estimates even if uncertainty (precision) is high because reproducibility conditions of measuring emission factors should include the possible climate, animal and management conditions usually occurring on the farm. On housing scale, activity data of the farm during the observation period and during the extrapolation period can be used provided the measurand is accurately defined (e.g. take into account key indicators such as the number of lactating cows, their liveweight, milk production and feed, the other animals present in the house, the grazing periods). On category scale, sampling the gases inside and outside the house and sampling the farms according to their variability in activity data and management can be used to improve the representativeness of emission factors deduced from emission measurements and models of animal production.

4 Results from the measurement campaign in a pig farm in the Netherlands (A2.3.5) (WR)

4.1 Information on the pig barn, The Netherlands

Measurements were performed at a commercial pig farm in the south of the country (exact location not disclosed for privacy reasons). The farm has a closed production system, so both reproduction and rearing of

pigs takes place. For the campaign, two fattening pigs units (and two for weaned piglets) could be used, one conventional and the other with measures to reduce emissions at the source. The main differences are tilted side walls in the manure pit to reduce manure surface and thus NH_3 , which is then removed to a digester daily to reduce CH_4 and increase biogas production.

4.2 Description of setup for the field measurement campaign

Placement of devices in or around the pig units firstly depends on sampling principle (passive or active by means of a pump). Passive units will have to be placed in the airflow towards the fan, by rule of thumb at a distance of ~ 50 cm both vertically and horizontally. Also, the use of an inlet ring around the fan is desirable, as this provides a more laminar airflow. Power and data cables are led through the wall to a data logger, which transmits the data to the central WR storage at least daily. The left panel of Figure 32 shows the setup inside one of the pig units used in this study.

PE tubing is used for actively sampling devices, which were then placed on a shelf in the corridor leading to the pig units (right panel of Figure 32). Tubing was kept as short as possible, and left unheated as risk of condensation was deemed low. Each device had its' own tube equipped with a dust filter to prevent soiling of the flow/measurement path, additional to any internal filters. Additional tubes were installed from which reference samples can be taken, seen as bundles in the picture below.

Figure 32. Installed sensors seen inside (left) and outside (right) the pig unit.

4.3 Flow measurements

As a direct measurement of flow through logging of working fans' frequency or the use of measurement fans was unavailable, the CO_2 mass balance method has been applied instead. With the two fattening pig units having their own air inlet, a CO_2 sensor was placed at each of those. Similarly, sensors were placed in the air stream towards the fan in both units, approximately 50 cm below and to the side. This ensures measurement is taken at a representative spot while avoiding turbulence from the fan itself.

For fattening pigs, the CO_2 production is calculated as follows:

$$PCO_2 (\text{fattening pigs}) = \text{conversion factor} \times \left(5.09m^{0.75} + (1 - (0.47 + 0.03 \times m)) \times (n \times 5.09m^{0.75} - 5.09m^{0.75}) \right), \quad (1)$$

where

PCO ₂	=	CO ₂ production in m ³ CO ₂ /h
Conversion factor	=	total heat production to CO ₂ production in m ³ CO ₂ /h per heat production unit; 0.185 at animal and 0.200 at barn level
m	=	average weight of the animals in kg
n	=	daily energy intake in times the maintenance requirement

For traditional housing the conversion factor at barn level was used, with source measures at animal level as manure is removed daily. Average weight is derived by interpolating from start weight (registered by the farmer) or average weight at delivery (taken from yearly management overview). The feeding level for fattening pigs was set at 2.96 times maintenance at the start decreasing to 2.33 at the end of the production round. In case of weaned piglets, a constant value of 3 is assumed.

4.4 Reference measurements

To account for any interferences that might occur under field conditions, WR deploys its' sensors in conjunction with regular reference measurements (typically bimonthly) over a 24 period. For ammonia, these consist of air sampling using impingers where ammonia is bound by an acid to be photometrically analysed in the laboratory. Greenhouse gases are sampled using the lung method, and analysis by gas chromatography. These methods were described in detail in Mosquera et al. (2019) and Mosquera et al. (2020) respectively.

In order to derive the calibration for a given sensor, its' (semi) 24h average over the period reference sampling took place is calculated. This means a reference measurement can be started any time of the day and provides some leeway in exact duration (+/- 1 hour). Calibration to be applied is then found by linear regression and is in the form of $y = a \cdot x + b$. Measurements and thus reference sampling at this location have continued after the campaign, providing extra data points for the correction.

4.5 Tested sensors

For testing, WR received from project partners:

- 2 Senseair K96 CH₄/CO₂/H₂O sensors (serial numbers 1138E and 1149F)
- 1 Senseair K96 N₂O/CO₂/H₂O sensor (serial number 115B5)
- 2 Senseair NH₃/CO₂ sensors (serial numbers 26A and 26C)
- 1 Gasera ONE CH₄/CO₂/N₂O/NH₃/H₂O prototype
- 2 Vaisala Indigo520 loggers with 4 HMP7 T/RH probes

These have been described in more detail in sections 3.5.1 to 3.5.3. One of each was allocated to the fattening pigs with traditional housing, with remaining sensors being deployed in the unit where source measures have been taken. As the Indigo devices have two T/RH probes attached one was used to monitor both units with fattening pigs, and the other similarly units with weaned piglets.

In each unit a set of equipment WR routinely uses for continuous emission monitoring was deployed, together with other sensors under test (not reported further here):

- Dräger Polytron® 8100 EC for NH_3
- ABB EasyLine 3020 for CH_4
- Vaisala GMP252 for CO_2
- Vaisala HMP60 for T/RH

When CH_4 concentrations to be measured are expected to be low, the Axetris LGD Compact-A is used instead (as was the case for the dairy campaigns in Finland). Also, CO_2 is measured at every air inlet, here the fattening pig units having separate intakes while the weaned piglets shared the same one.

4.6 Results

Figure 33. Fattening pig results overview, using field calibrated sensor data from WR (Dräger Polytron 8100 EC for NH₃, ABB EasyLine 3020 for CH₄, Vaisala GMP252 for CO₂ and Vaisala HMP60 for T/RH; note: as HMP60 in unit with source measures was broken, HMP7 results are shown instead).

As can be seen in above Figure 33 sensor installation took place on October 17th 2024, but due to a technical issue the Dräger NH₃ followed a week later (October 23rd). The T/RH sensor deployed in the fattening pig unit with source measures was found to be defective after the campaign. In the graphs it is replaced by the HMP7,

which showed to be in good agreement with both sensors in the same and other units. Due to an error with the settings, first week of results is however missing.

Production rounds in both units were not in sync, with the round in the unit with source measures starting October 23rd while one was ongoing in the traditional unit until November 4th. After this cleaning took place (seen by the high humidity recorded), after which – at the farmers’ discretion – unit was left unoccupied for a fairly long period. As the unit shares a manure pit, still some NH₃ and CH₄ was measured during this time before the new round started November 26th. Tentatively speaking source measures however seem to be effective, as concentrations remained below the traditional unit even with round progressing during over the duration of the campaign (although also being slightly cooler).

4.6.1 4.6.1 Sensor comparison

Daily averages were calculated, as shown in Figure 34 for the sensors installed in the traditional fattening pig unit. Similar graphs for the unit with source measures are available but not shown here for brevity.

Figure 34. Daily values of field calibrated WR sensors and post-processed data from Gasera and Senseair.

Senseair sensor 26A showed initial drift for NH_3 but good agreement for CO_2 , before developing a suspected flow problem end October. The K96 device for $\text{N}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2$ continued this over the whole period, but like the Gasera experienced difficulties with N_2O . With respect to NH_3 , CH_4 and CO_2 there was generally good agreement between Gasera and WR sensors. The HMP7 T/RH probe showed an increase in temperature seemingly during cleaning of the unit after production round finished. Inspection of data did not reveal obvious artefacts, so remains unclear whether this is a coincidence like something producing heat near the sensor or another interference. Between RH measured by the WR and Vaisala probes an offset exists, but error in these measurements might be substantial to start with.

As the Senseair and Gasera devices were all prototypes and development will continue with help of the data generated during the field campaigns, no further (formal) data checks were performed at this point.

4.6.2 Emission estimation

From the ventilation rate established as described in Section 4.3 and daily averages of the sensors in the previous section, emissions can be calculated after conversion of ppm in mg/m^3 . At standard temperature (20°C) and pressure (1013 mbar) these are 0.71 and 0.67 for NH_3 and CH_4 respectively. These are then usually expressed in $\text{kg}/\text{animal place}/\text{year}$, in order to make comparison to established emission factors possible. Interpretation of emissions on daily vs. yearly basis however should be done with great care, as moment in the production cycle and (environmental) conditions will have a profound effect.

With this exercise, emissions of NH_3 from traditionally housed fattening pigs starting from around 0.6 $\text{kg}/\text{animal place}/\text{year}$ nearing 3.0 kg towards the end of the round were found. For CH_4 there figures were 9 $\text{kg}/\text{animal place}/\text{year}$ at the start to between 12 and 13 $\text{kg}/\text{animal place}/\text{year}$ at the end. With source measures applied, NH_3 emission remained in the range of 0.3-0.6 $\text{kg}/\text{animal place}/\text{year}$ during the period observed, with CH_4 varying around 3-4 $\text{kg}/\text{animal place}/\text{year}$. This proves measures taken were effective, although emissions from the manure now being processed and stored elsewhere still need to be prevented.

4.7 Conclusion and observations from the field measurements (WR)

During the pig campaign prototype sensors or devices from Senseair and Gasera were deployed under regular monitoring conditions. This was done alongside commercially available sensors with which ample experience already exists. Also, these are being subjected to, and field calibrated towards regular reference measurements through wet chemical (NH_3) or gas chromatography (greenhouse gases) analyses. Resulting data has shown good agreement for some components, but also room for improvement on others. In such, results are very valuable to be used towards further development as indicated by the manufacturers.

Emissions calculated from the measurements taken led to credible figures, although this should be maintained for longer periods (production round or a year) for a better estimation. Nevertheless, the source measures taken in one of the fattening pig units seemed to be effective. With regards to determining the flow, improvements to the CO_2 production model might still be possible through information farmers are able to provide and model parameterization. This concerns animal numbers and exact start and end weights, but also characteristics like feeding schedule or the growth curve. Direct flow registration is also possible, through regular wind speed measurements, frequency logging (sometimes already in place) or measurement fans. However, these methods will also come with their challenges.

5 Results from remote measurements (A2.3.6) (TNO, VSL, WR)

5.1 VSL activities in remote measurement method campaigns

VSL supported TNO by providing the mobile ammonia generator (the so-called TRACTOR (TRaceable Ammonia CalibraTOR) developed in WP1; Figure 35) for the field study in Middenmeer, the Netherlands and for laboratory and field tests at TNO in Petten. The main focus was on the testing of the two Healthy Photon instruments that are based on tunable diode laser spectroscopy with an open multi-pass cell. These instruments are well-suited for measurements of ammonia concentrations as no sampling lines are needed. The main outcomes of this part of the study were:

- Healthy Photon system one: This system had an offset of +30 ppb. After correcting for this offset a good agreement was obtained between the spectrometer response and the generated amount fractions by the TRACTOR
- Healthy Photon system two: This system had no offset but the response was 50% too low. Again, after correcting for this a good agreement was obtained between the spectrometer response and the generated amount fractions by the TRACTOR
- In the lab it is possible to use a closed cell to calibrate the Healthy Photon systems. In the field it not yet ideal due to leakages in the cell while the wind speeds were high and it also is quite time-consuming to reach equilibrium in a 334 liter volume cell. At least 1.5 hour is needed to do better calibration at the time of the field study. A better leak-tight enclosure is needed to calibrate the Healthy Photon systems in the field. But when weather conditions allowed, one 3-day long field calibration was conducted in TNO Petten lab outside.
- During the field study also some brief tests with two Aerodyne systems from UKCEH. These systems use a closed multi-pass cell but are operated at extremely high flow rates of ~14 L/min to obtain a rapid response. The experiments in the field showed that indeed both these systems had a very fast time response: almost directly (about 2 seconds) after generating ammonia with the TRACTOR a response was seen with the systems. The reported ammonia concentrations were in line with the generated ammonia concentrations after correcting for the dilution with atmospheric air (the TRACTOR can generate only maximum 8 L/min while these Aerodyne systems suck in nearly twice this flow rate).

Figure 35. a) VSL TRACTOR system set-up at the TNO Petten laser lab indoor calibrating TNO mobile HT and flux HT, in both cases the 3.7 Liters closed glass cell was used for HT systems; b) The RGM system outside the TNO Petten lab to calibrate TNO mobile HT after the 1st remote measurement close-by a dairy farm; c) The RGM system calibrated UKCEH flux HT during the campaign period close-by a dairy farm.

5.2 TNO's remote measurement results

We evaluated our remote mobile measurement techniques to quantify the ammonia (NH_3) and methane (CH_4) emission rates of a dairy farm in the Netherlands. The tests were performed during the quantiAGREMI field campaign of WP3.

Our approach to determine the farm emission rate from mobile measurements was based on the Tracer Dispersion Method (TDM), which involves the release of a known quantity of tracer gas (nitrous oxide, N_2O). In this method, the emission rates of the target gases are estimated from the measured concentration ratios of the target and tracer gases. The approach was tested during the campaign period. For evaluation, we used the day that included on-site field calibrations, which is reported here.

The measured concentration levels of the tracer gas and the source gas is influenced by the turbulence downwind of the source, these are controlled by meteorological conditions, including wind direction, wind speed, humidity, and temperature, measurement distance. But the tracer method assumes that these effects work in the same way on both components. This assumption holds if the tracer position is well chosen. And the uncertainty reported here is representative of such a situation. In addition, to evaluate background N_2O levels, measurements are taken without the use of tracers first. This step is crucial to determine the baseline N_2O concentration. Typically, the N_2O emitted from the farm is minimal, ranging from only 1 to 3 ppb above background levels when it is measured at 200 meters away. In contrast, the tracer concentrations are significantly higher, usually between 50 to 100 ppb above background. When the farm's N_2O emissions are this low, the tracer plumes can be directly used for emission calculations. Second, if there are significant N_2O emissions from the manure storage, we place the tracer outside the wind field of the main N_2O plume, ensuring the tracer is released away from the primary emission source. As long as the manure storage emissions do not overlap with those from the farm building, the tracer method can still be applied to estimate CH_4 and NH_3 emissions accurately.

The results of this campaign demonstrated the effectiveness of the tracer dispersion method (TDM) for quantifying dairy farm emissions. A common approach for estimating overall emissions is the calculation of unweighted mean values. In this study, based on 21 plumes, the unweighted means were $0.096 \pm 0.009 \text{ g s}^{-1}$ for NH_3 and $0.80 \pm 0.062 \text{ g s}^{-1}$ for CH_4 , with relative errors of 7.8% and 9.1%, respectively. In contrast, applying individual plume error propagation yielded weighted mean emission rates, where a greater weight was assigned to larger plumes with lower associated uncertainty. The weighted estimates were $0.069 \pm 0.001 \text{ g s}^{-1}$ for NH_3 and $0.62 \pm 0.01 \text{ g s}^{-1}$ for CH_4 , with substantially lower relative errors of 2% and 1%, respectively. Regardless of the averaging method, the NH_3 -to- CH_4 emission ratio was consistently determined as 0.110 ± 0.004 on the day with reliable data. For comparison, indoor daily measurements conducted by WR reported similar emission values of 0.075 g s^{-1} for NH_3 and 0.68 g s^{-1} for CH_4 .

These findings highlight both the robustness of the tracer method and the need for further refinements in measurement practices. In particular, the newly developed VSL system helped to calibrate HT more accurately and precisely. Improved NH_3 calibration procedures under high-humidity conditions and the extension of N_2O calibration ranges are required to ensure reliable performance across diverse field environments. Furthermore, the current analysis has noticed that temperature variations influence mainly on the offset of the HT open-path NH_3 analyser, with limited affecting on the calibration slope but not none. Such impact can be addressed by using a temperature-controlled water-cooling system for HT, especially under cold field environments. TNO presented detailed methods and results during the project, which are documented in a publicly available TNO report (Zhang et al.,2025).

5.3 Conclusions

TNO effectively applied the TDM method for mobile emission measurements using N₂O as a tracer to quantify NH₃ and CH₄ emissions from a dairy farm. To estimate the accuracy of this method for estimating farm emissions, an uncertainty evaluation was performed on all measured input parameters for the emission rate.

The mobile CH₄ and N₂O concentrations were measured with a TILDAS dual-laser analyser with calibration-related uncertainties below 1% relative. The NH₃ concentrations were measured with the open-path HT-analyser, for which the calibration was performed within this project with the VSL RGM system. From this NH₃ calibration an estimate of the uncertainty in the data from the HT-system followed, related to HT instrument signal noise, slope, offset, temperature effects, and baseline artefacts, and VSL system error. Overall, relative uncertainties in CH₄, N₂O and NH₃ concentrations were estimated at 2%, 13% and 6%, respectively.

To reduce these uncertainties in future, it is recommended to perform NH₃ calibration under higher humidity conditions with other open-path instruments (e.g. miniDOAS) and to increase the range of N₂O concentration values for the tracer calibration.

Based on 21 plume transect measurements of all three gases, taking into account that some transects had larger uncertainty, weighted emission rates of 0.62 ± 0.019 g/s for CH₄ and 0.067 ± 0.002 g/s for NH₃ were found.

6 Interpretation of results from campaigns (A2.3.7) (INRAE, WR, TNO, VSL)

6.1 Emission factors assessment (INRAE, WR)

An emission factor (EF) is defined as the rate of emission per unit of activity. For example, in this project focusing on animal housing, EF used in national inventories can be expressed as kg NH₃·kg TAN⁻¹ (TAN: total ammoniacal nitrogen), kg N₂O·kg excreted N⁻¹, or kg CH₄·kg excreted VS⁻¹ (VS: volatile solids). EF is established based on emissions rates measurement and activity data.

The quantification of EF is required for national inventories or policy implementation tools that classify livestock systems into categories (often based on housing type, animal and manure management, and climatic conditions; e.g. Luostarinen et al., 2017). Tools used for farm-level environmental assessments have been developed using the same EF as those used in inventories (e.g. Cool Farm Tool: Vidican et al., 2022; NZ farm emission method, MPI, 2024). However, variables such as TAN can be difficult to measure on farms because of sampling and annual representativeness issues. It introduces uncertainty sources between SI-traceable activity data such as commercialized products and SI-traceable measurements of NH₃ emissions.

Therefore, the representativeness of EF is crucial to accurately reflect field conditions and to support the development of mitigation strategies adapted to specific livestock systems. This representativeness of EF can only be achieved if livestock categories/systems are well characterized and the influence of key indicators identified. In the case of farm-specific assessments, the production process on the farm should be precisely described and an emission model calibrated on its production process to reflect the influence of its activity on emissions (Tier 2 or Tier 3 approach according to inventory terminology). An EF cannot be derived from a single measurement campaign. To estimate reliable values, emission models must be validated in several representative animal houses of a given category, at different times throughout the year (a multi-site, multi-period sampling approach). Furthermore, it is not sufficient to simply average individual measurements to obtain annual EF because they reflect one occurrence of production activity and climate and not their probability distribution. Seasonal dynamics (e.g., temperature or humidity effects), manure management practices, and growth stages (for growing animals) must also be accounted for, with appropriate weighting of the emission data. Therefore, we recommend to use measurement models with multiple outputs (GUM-8,

JCGM 102:2011), including all targeted emissions among outputs and animal products among inputs, to assess uncertainties in future work on EF on farm scale.

This means that measurement methods must be capable of covering a wide range of situations and must produce results with uncertainties low enough to ensure representativeness for the targeted livestock categories/systems. It also implies that information related to measurement conditions and system characteristics must be systematically reported to reduce definitional uncertainty and be sure that given EF are attributed to the right category (see D2, Target Application TA1).

The measurement methods implemented in this project provide access to emission rates at different time resolutions. After measurement, these emission rates have to be aggregated or interpolated and extrapolated (to the whole rearing period or one year), depending on the methods, to derive EF. These different stages will also give rise to additional uncertainties that will need to be assessed and incorporated into the final result. An additional model is needed to derive EF from emissions calculated during observation period. The influencing factors mentioned in D4 that influence the emissions from housing are (i) information from farm on production process and (ii) information on environmental conditions. To estimate SI-traceable EF, the models used to deduce EF from observed periods and sites should use SI-traceable inputs (“unbroken chain of calibrations”; VIM, JCGM 200:2012).

For remote measurement methods, such as the one implemented by TNO, these provide snapshots of emission rates at a specific point in time. These SI-traceable emission rates can be used for verification after conversion into EF with activity data corresponding to the moment of each measurement are available and with biological and physical variables influencing landscape deposition and emissions between the source and the measuring position. The additional model needed to derive EF from emissions calculated during observation period should use the factors influencing the emissions from housing and also the factors mentioned in D5 that influence the deposition and emissions between the source and the observation area (i) information of the biological processes and (ii) information on environmental conditions. When these influencing factors are not discussed, the average EF obtained may not be fully representative of the studied system and will be associated with significant uncertainty due to interpolation between measurement periods and the extrapolation to the year. When these factors are deduced from SI-traceable measurements, the accuracy of the bottom-up EF deduced from such extrapolation model can be used to validate EF deduced from top-down approaches. Thus, to check the reliability of the EF on landscape scale, both bottom-up and top-down approaches using general circulation models and SI-traceable satellite observations (e.g. using Fiducial Reference Measurements and methods; CEOS, 2025) after incorporating landscape–atmosphere interactions under varying climatic conditions (wind, precipitation, fog) could be used.

For housing with mechanical ventilation and permanently confined animals, houses can be equipped with ventilation and gas concentration sensors provided the installation and use of these equipment will not induce higher environmental impact than expected reduction in emissions. Direct registration is best, as it will reflect continuously the housing emissions as shown by WR during the pig farm campaign. However with measurement fans, calibration control should be implemented from time to time. Logging the frequency of working fans is another option. The CO₂-production model could also be used as control of ventilation measurement trueness because with digitalization more and more information becomes available and can be linked to emission measurements. If this option is implemented careful calibration of model parameters should be chosen, including regular reconsideration and perhaps updates based on region, animal breed or housing (firstly manure storage inside or outside the building).

For housing with variable presence of animals (grazing of cattle or outdoor access of poultry), farm level estimates of animal presence and manure removal are key indicators of the amount excreted in the house. Field campaigns in Finland (LUKE farm) and Switzerland (Agroscope farm, see Deliverable 2) showed that NH₃ concentrations decrease slowly after dairy cows went to grazing while CO₂ concentrations decreased more rapidly. It shows that soiled areas continue to emit NH₃ until manure has dried. This physical process is expected to depend on ventilation, air humidity and manure quantity. As these key indicators are farm-dependent and difficult to monitor on annual scale in a cost-effective way, we recommend to evaluate nitrogen

excretion and conservation in the manure (mass balance approach) to estimate whether this loss is significant or not on specific farms.

To address a progressive improvement in annual emission factors and contribution of animal housing emissions in inventories, we proposed using 3 levels (Robin et al., 2024). The first level starts with on-going situation. The second level 2 introduces QA/QC procedures to make sure the trueness of calculated emissions and the choice of “standard animal productions” to reduce definitional uncertainties of categories used to report emissions in inventories (e.g. starting and ending weight of the “growing-finishing pig”; weight and milk production of “lactating cow”). It is divided in two sublevels. In the first one (level 2a), influencing factors depending on feed-animal-manure-climate interactions would be better described at house/farm scale (reduce uncertainty of model inputs such as grazing time for dairy cattle, nitrogen “excess” in feed, rearing duration of animals for meat production). In the second one (level 2b) a choice of granularity (house/farm/production chain, other...) allows collection and verification of data and emission factors through random field verification of both influencing factors and emissions in order to check and/or improve the trueness of EF. The third level use annual programs of field verifications to update the categories most impacting the national reductions in emissions (scientific literature is used to improve sampling design, influencing factors, emission measuring methods but EF are definitely deduced from routine and representative on-farm measurements).

6.2 Uncertainty analysis (INRAE, WR, TNO, VSL)

Emission factors, like any measurement, should, when published, be accompanied by an estimate of uncertainty, enabling potential users to assess the quality and reliability of the reported value with respect to its intended use.

As described in the previous section, the emission factor of a given livestock building is derived from measurements of gas emission rates emitted by the building, which are aggregated or interpolated over a defined time period (e.g., a year or a full production cycle). These aggregated emission rates are then normalized to an activity variable such as nitrogen excreted, animal unit, or live weight (kg LW).

Each step of this process introduces uncertainty. These uncertainties can be grouped into two main categories:

1. **Measurement-related uncertainty**, arising from the accuracy of the flux measurement techniques and from the temporal aggregation of flux data; and
2. **Activity data uncertainty**, linked to the precision and representativeness of the underlying activity information.

6.2.1 Measurement-related uncertainty

According to *ISO 5725*, two terms—*trueness* and *precision*—are used to describe the accuracy of a measurement method. *Trueness* refers to the closeness of agreement between the mean of a large number of test results and the accepted reference value, while *precision* expresses the closeness of agreement between repeated measurements under specified conditions (ISO 5725-1: 2023).

For methods applied to animal housing, *precision* is generally evaluated based on information provided with the measurement devices used to record the input variables of the model used to calculate the measurand (here, the emission rate). However, depending on the approach (see deliverable D2), it is also necessary to account for additional sources of uncertainty beyond instrumental accuracy, such as the effect of dust on filters at the entrance of the sampling lines or the effect of sensors position in the building.

INRAE and LNE performed such an evaluation using an existing dataset for a past experiment with broilers in controlled conditions (Annex 1). With this data set, hourly CO₂ emission rates (m³.h) were calculated as indicated in equation 2.

$$Q_{CO_2}^n = \frac{Q_{air} \times \rho_{air} \times ([CO_2]_{in} - [CO_2]_{out})}{\rho_{norm}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

With

$$Q_{CO_2} : \text{CO}_2 \text{ emission } [kg \text{ CO}_2/h]$$

$$Q_{air} : \text{Air flow rate } [m^3/h]$$

$$\rho_{air} : \text{Humid air density } [kg/m^3]$$

$$\rho_{norm} : \text{Standardised air density (T=20°C, P=101325Pa and RH=60\%)} [kg/m^3]$$

$$[CO_2]_{in} : \text{Inside CO}_2 \text{ concentration } [kg \text{ CO}_2/m^3]$$

$$[CO_2]_{out} : \text{Outside CO}_2 \text{ concentration } [kg \text{ CO}_2/m^3]$$

The Uncertainty calculations for this measurand was calculated following GUM 6 (equation 2).

$$u_c(Q_{CO_2}) = Q_{CO_2} \times \sqrt{\left(\frac{u(Q_{air})}{Q_{air}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u([CO_2]_{in})}{\Delta CO_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u([CO_2]_{out})}{\Delta CO_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(\rho_{air})}{\rho_{air}}\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Figure 36 presents the identified uncertainty sources in relation with the measurement conditions and the measurement method that has been implemented.

Figure 36: Fish bone diagram, analysis of uncertainty sources for the hourly C_{CO_2} emission rate in a experimental broiler house

INRAE and LNE evaluated that the precision of measurement was approximately 30%, primarily due to uncertainty in the ventilation rate, which was identified as the dominant source of error (

Table 1).

Table 1. Uncertainty evaluation of Hourly CO_2 _C emission rates and of the variables in the model used to assess this measurand

Variable	Maximum Relative uncertainty
Q_{CO_2}	30%
Q_{air}	27%
$[CO_2]_{in}$	5%
$[CO_2]_{out}$	5%
ρ_{air}	<1%

The precision of the cumulative CO_2 emission over the rearing period (sum of hourly emission rates), which is the relevant measurand for EF assessment, was however below 10%.

The evaluation of *trueness* relies on the possibility of comparing measured emissions with a reference or benchmark value (e.g., a theoretical/reference maximum). As discussed in Deliverable 2, for livestock buildings, cumulative emissions of carbon- and nitrogen-based compounds over a given period can be compared to the mass balance deficit of corresponding elemental mass balances calculated for the same period. These mass balances are constructed from farm-specific data, some of which are well characterized (e.g., feed input, animal weights, milk yield) because they are critical for farm management and economic viability, whereas others are less accessible (e.g. quantity and chemical composition of manure) but can be estimated using reference values or additional measurements.

INRAE and LNE present an evaluation of *trueness* for the same dataset used for precision assessment. A difference of approximately 20% (Figure 37) was found between the carbon mass balance deficit over the rearing period and the cumulative CO₂-C emissions (in the experiment CH₄-C were negligible). Since the uncertainty associated with the carbon mass balance deficit was estimated at 10%, corrections were applied to the measured airflow rates (based on knowledge of the ventilation system operation and the maximum fan flow capacities) in order to best align the measured emissions with those estimated from the mass balance. Emissions of other gases were then recalculated using the corrected airflow data. The uncertainty associated with cumulative emissions for each gas was subsequently derived from both measurement precision and the uncertainty of the corresponding elemental mass balance deficit. Further work on this topic is ongoing.

Figure 37: Comparison of cumulative CO₂-C emissions from measurement and mass balance calculations

INRAE and LNE proposed an approach to improve the accuracy of emissions rates measurement and identify the main source of uncertainty in the measurand model (here the ventilation rate). This approach could be extended to the different measurement methods implemented within the project and described in Deliverable 2. Thanks to the evaluation of trueness, they also proposed an approach to improve the final accuracy by modifying the procedure for analysing the measurement results and for calculating the emission rates and the cumulative emissions (annex 1).

The evaluation of measurement uncertainty is inherently complex. Therefore, it should be explicitly documented in all publications reporting emission measurements, or, alternatively, a standardized and recognized procedure should be referenced—although such a standard is currently lacking for the types of methods used in this project. The robustness of the final uncertainty estimate depends on the number and nature of uncertainty sources considered, the weighting and values assigned to each, and the propagation method applied. Transparent reporting of these aspects would enable recalculation of uncertainties under alternative assumptions, enhance reproducibility, and facilitate the comparison of emission measurements published across different studies.

The TNO remote measurement method for estimating NH₃ and CH₄ emission uncertainties is detailed below. Errors in the measured and calibrated NH₃, CH₄, and N₂O concentrations were quantified using standard error propagation (*c.f. Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, 2008, sec. 5.1.2*).

The TILDAS dual-laser analyser (Aerodyne Research, USA) was field-calibrated using two ICOS-traceable gas standards with high and low CH₄ and N₂O concentrations. Stable measurement periods were used for linear regression after outlier removal. Uncertainties in CH₄ and N₂O measurements mainly stem from

calibration gas accuracy, instrument handling, and regression fitting. Total absolute uncertainties were ~4.4 ppb for CH₄ and ~1.5 ppb for N₂O (0.2 – 0.4% relative). During plume measurements, relative uncertainties averaged 2 ± 1% for CH₄ and 13 ± 4% for N₂O, decreasing with higher concentrations. These uncertainties were used in the propagation of total NH₃ emission errors using standard root-sum-square methods later.

NH₃ was measured using the TNO mobile HT system, pre- and post-calibrated by VSL. Plume analysis and uncertainty propagation involved integrating baseline-corrected NH₃ concentrations over time, with the baseline defined by linear regression between plume start and end points. NH₃ plumes were baseline-corrected, VSL-calibrated, and temperature-adjusted before uncertainty propagation. Total relative errors averaged ~5.5%, mainly driven by instrument noise (~85% of the total error), while baseline and calibration factors contributed less than 10%. This confirms that signal noise is the dominant source of uncertainty in NH₃ plume measurements. An example of the first NH₃ plume (Figure 38) shows a total plume integral of 223 ppb with a 12 ppb error (5.4%) and a net plume integral of 228 ppb with a 12.8 ppb error (5.6%). In both cases, signal noise dominated the uncertainty (~ 88 – 95%), while baseline and other factors contributed less than 10%, confirming noise as the primary error source.

Figure 38. Time series of 1st calibrated NH₃ concentration total plume on Oct 2nd in the left; and its error decomposition in the left (upper plots). And time series of the Net NH₃ concentration plume after removing background in the left; and its error decomposition in the right (lower plots).

Across all 21 measured plumes, total error per net NH₃ plume averaged 14.3 ± 0.6 ppb, with a relative error of 5.5 ± 0.3%. These errors depended on plume duration and background level, reflecting consistent measurement precision across the dataset.

Furthermore, NH₃ and CH₄ emission rates for individual plumes were calculated using the N₂O TDM method (Equations 4 and 5), with corresponding error propagation applied to quantify uncertainties.

$$Q_{NH_3} = Q_{N_2O} \cdot \frac{M_{NH_3}}{M_{N_2O}} \cdot \frac{\int S_{NH_3}}{\int S_{N_2O}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$Q_{CH_4} = Q_{N_2O} \cdot \frac{M_{CH_4}}{M_{N_2O}} \cdot \frac{\int S_{CH_4}}{\int S_{N_2O}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Where:

- Q_{NH_3} , Q_{CH_4} are estimated NH_3 and CH_4 emission rate, respectively;
- Q_{N_2O} is known tracer (N_2O) emission rate;
- M is molar mass of each gas (constant);
- $\int S$ is integrated concentration signal (area under curve for plume) for each gas.

The errors in these emission rates are primarily related to two sources:

1. The uncertainty in the tracer emission rate Q_{N_2O} , which can result from flow control and weighing accuracy (roughly estimated to be $\pm 2\%$).
2. The integrated signals of NH_3 , CH_4 and N_2O ($\int S$) are subject to uncertainty due to instrument noise, calibration results, temperature drifting and calibration reference instrument system error.

Additionally, the definition of plume start and end times can indirectly affect the final error ratio, and also the method used for background subtraction.

Here, the relative error $\sigma_{Q_{NH_3}}$ and $\sigma_{Q_{CH_4}}$ in Q_{NH_3} and Q_{CH_4} for each individual NH_3 and CH_4 plume traverse can be given using Equations 6 and 7 below:

$$\sigma_{Q_{NH_3}} = Q_{NH_3} \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{Q_{N_2O}}}{Q_{N_2O}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\int S_{NH_3}}}{\int S_{NH_3}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\int S_{N_2O}}}{\int S_{N_2O}}\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\sigma_{Q_{CH_4}} = Q_{CH_4} \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{Q_{N_2O}}}{Q_{N_2O}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\int S_{CH_4}}}{\int S_{CH_4}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\int S_{N_2O}}}{\int S_{N_2O}}\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

With individual plume emissions ($Q_i_{NH_3}$ or $Q_i_{CH_4}$) and their uncertainties σ_i available, all plumes represent measurements of the same source under similar conditions, and a statistically sound estimate of the average emission rate and its total uncertainty can be best estimated used weighted mean and the uncertainty of weighted mean in below. This method gives more weight to more precise plumes (with lower σ_i).

$$\hat{Q}_{\text{Weighted}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{Q_i}{\sigma_i^2}\right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\sigma_{\hat{Q}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}\right)}} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

The error estimation can be done per plume. In the end, the weighted mean of NH_3 and CH_4 emissions are (0.067 ± 0.002) g/s and (0.62 ± 0.019) g/s, with rather small uncertainty as the relative error for NH_3 and CH_4 estimated emissions were about 3.2% and 3.0%. Consequently, the remotely measured emissions ratio of $NH_3:CH_4$ for this single-day cattle farm observation was 0.12 ± 0.004 .

6.2.2 Activity data uncertainty

Activity data must also be collected at the time of emission rates measurements. They are useful not only for interpreting the measured emission rates but also for calculating emission factors. Some of these data will come from direct observations, such as the number of animals present during the measurements. Some will be provided by the farmer, for example, the amounts of feed consumed, the time of grazing or the animals' weight during the measurement period. Some can come from SI-traceable measurements such as the mass of milk collected by a company or the daily production of milk per cow measured with traceable instruments.

These data will either be used directly to calculate the emission factor (EF) or serve as intermediate variables for estimating a quantity of interest, such as the amount of nitrogen excreted. The uncertainty associated with these activity data will therefore have a direct impact on the uncertainty of the calculated emission factor. That means that accurate measurement of emissions rates is not enough to have an accurate EF.

The availability of activity data will vary depending on the measurement conditions and the farmer's availability. Webb et al. (2023) proposed a list of relevant activity data to be collected but also equations for EF unit conversion. Their list reflects research activity where experimental conditions have well monitored animals. In the case of measurements during commercial activity, hazards such as animal mortality, diseases, heat stress also influence the relationship between feed input, animal and manure production, farmer management practices and gaseous emissions. To reflect accurately these hazards, expertise of farm advisors should be considered to add a list of relevant activity data that influence the variability of production between years and between farms. These data could then be used to improve the assessment of random measurement uncertainty of housing emissions and correct potential bias of representativeness of measurement days.

Lastly, the TNO remote measurement approach used here captures the bulk plume from all emission sources within the observed area. When the goal is to assess the contribution from a specific livestock farm, it will be necessary to separate individual sources. To achieve such separation, proper placement of the N_2O tracer and careful selection of wind direction and driving routes are key. Additionally, $NH_3:CH_4$ emission ratios (which differ between source types) may be used to distinguish different NH_3 plumes, while information on farm activities such as manure spreading, etc. are needed as well. However, if the goal is merely to evaluate the overall emission impact on the surrounding environment, then the total combined emissions are the relevant measure.

6.3 Involvement regarding farm management systems and farmer management tools to monitor emission levels (INRAE)

Several objectives can be identified in livestock facilities that justify the implementation of gas sensors:

1. Monitoring of the indoor environment in closed buildings
2. Spot verification of emission levels (for regulatory compliance or management support)

6.3.1 Monitoring of the Indoor Environment

Monitoring the concentrations of gases in livestock buildings can significantly contribute to improve indoor air conditions, reduce risks, and contribute to animal and worker welfare. It can also have economic benefits, given the potential impact of elevated gas concentrations on animal growth performance.

Higher prevalence of respiratory diseases has been reported among farmers — particularly pig and poultry producers — and the link with occupational exposure has been documented since the 1990s–2000s (HSE, 2002; Kovignas et al., 1999; Omland, 2002; Laplante, 2007; Donham, 2010). The most studied pathologies are asthma, chronic bronchitis, and decline in lung function, investigated through various study designs (longitudinal studies, before/after workday assessments, etc.). Significant associations have been found with exposure to dust, ammonia (NH_3), and endotoxins.

Zhou et al. (2020) showed that exposure to 25 ppm and 35 ppm NH_3 for extended periods (7–21 days) has clear negative effects on broiler performance (growth, feed efficiency). Exposure to 15 ppm appears near a threshold where performance is not visibly affected over the entire period, but inflammatory responses already begin at this lower concentration.

Several experimental studies have also demonstrated the adverse effects of high CO_2 concentrations, considered independently (without combining with NH_3 , humidity, or temperature), on the health and mortality of broilers. For example, the incidence of ascites was significantly higher when CO_2 concentration exceeded 6,000 ppm compared to 2,500 ppm (McGovern, 2001). Similarly, exposure to 9,000 ppm CO_2 during the early life stage of broiler (first 14 days) negatively affected the final mortality rate at 42 days, compared with lower exposures (0, 3,000, or 6,000 ppm) (Olanrewaju et al., 2008).

In some countries, there are legal standards defining maximum gas concentrations in livestock buildings to ensure animal welfare. In France, for example, the Ministerial Decree of 28 June 2010 establishing the standards for the protection of broiler chickens sets maximum limits of 3,000 ppm CO_2 and 20 ppm NH_3 in the air, measured at animal height and maintained throughout the production cycle. This regulatory framework allows for spot inspections by the competent authorities.

For workers, there are legal permissible exposure limit (PEL) fixed for Europe but also in each country. For NH_3 , 20 ppm averaged over an 8-hour work shift, 50 averaged over a 15-minutes work shift (https://www.inrs.fr/publications/bdd/fichetox/fiche.html?refINRS=FICHETOX_16). For CO_2 (https://www.inrs.fr/publications/bdd/vlep/SubstanceVLEPAG.html?refINRS=VLEP_SUBSTANCE_144), 5,000 ppm averaged over an 8-hour workshift. These are the concentration levels that may be found in pig and poultry manure for these two gases.

Continuous monitoring of CO_2 and NH_3 offers several advantages for farmers:

- It ensures that ventilation is working properly.
- It lets you know whether you need to protect yourself before entering the building.
- It allows you to adjust your farming practices if conditions are regularly poor, or even throughout the entire farming period.

The sensors tested during this project appear to be well-suited for monitoring the concentration ranges of NH_3 and CO_2 typically observed in cattle and pig housing, as well as for the gas mixtures present in these environments. For indoor air monitoring, an accuracy on the order of 1 ppm to a few ppm is expected — a performance level that was achieved by all devices tested.

However, additional testing would be useful in poultry houses and pig units with potentially higher gas concentrations, such as during extreme outdoor temperature events.

Furthermore, the tests conducted so far were short-term, which does not allow full assessment of the effects of environmental conditions on sensor performance. A long-term follow-up (≈ 1 year) would be necessary to validate these conclusions.

Additional Recommendations for Sensor Use for concentrations monitoring

- Establish a deployment protocol specifying sampling methods for both continuous and spot monitoring.
- Provide real-time readings of measured concentrations to enable workers to implement protective measures or adjust ventilation in case of high values.
- Use easily movable measurement systems to allow sampling at various locations within the building.
- Implement calibration alerts to ensure reliable measurements over time and limit calibration drift.

6.3.2 Spot verification of emission levels (for regulatory compliance or management support)

Several reasons may justify conducting spot emission measurements on farms, particularly in livestock buildings: in the context of regulations related to the IED Directive, or for farms engaged in a low-carbon initiative.

Pig and poultry farms covered by the European IED Directive are required to comply with Emission Limit Values (ELVs) for NH_3 . Monitoring of these farms at the national level is currently carried out using calculation tools based on emission factors (EFs) representative of various categories of livestock, established according to species and physiological stages, as well as animal and manure management practices.

The emission measurement methods proposed in this project—particularly those developed by TNO and INRAE—could make it possible to verify, for a given farm, that the EF assigned to its livestock building in the calculation tools accurately reflects its average emission level within a reasonable uncertainty range. To establish an average value, a protocol similar to that proposed by Guingand et al. (2011) or Ponchant et al. (2008) should be defined, taking into account the production cycle duration and the animals' physiological stages. In naturally ventilated barns with outdoor access to animals, effect of air temperature and relative humidity, wind speed, presence of animals in the barn on the NH_3 emission should also be taken into account in the extrapolation model.

Several spot measurements could thus be carried out to obtain an average EF that accounts for variations in emission levels over the course of the production period.

Similarly, measurements could be performed on farms to verify the specific EFs for greenhouse gases and ammonia, which are used in carbon footprint tools such as **GEEP**² or **CAP2ER**³. These tools are used to conduct environmental assessments for farms wishing to engage in a low-carbon certification process.

Farms participating in this process must implement emission-reduction techniques identified in the scientific literature. Conducting on-farm measurements could help verify the effectiveness of these mitigation techniques and adjust practices in cases where their efficiency is lower than expected.

For both potential applications of the developed methods, detailed documents specifying the operational implementation—including data processing procedures and uncertainty assessment—must be made available to operators (consulting firms, administrative authorities).

6.3.3 Farm monitoring system

From above analyses and the work achieved during other actions of quantiAGREMI project, we propose a farm monitoring process (Figure 39) that could be compliant with national metrological infrastructure, allow assessment of the efficiency of mitigation strategies and allow cross-sectoral assessments of emissions such as those required within scope 3 carbon reporting.

² <https://geep.ifip.asso.fr>

³ <https://idele.fr/detail-article/cap2err>

Figure 39. First proposal of farm monitoring process (INRAE)

In this farm monitoring process the traceability is based on a combination of reference gas mixtures, reference gas concentration sensors, reference experiments with animals and reference models of animal production.

This first set of metrological expertise cannot apply to any farm because both the cost and the associated gas emissions would not be sustainable. Therefore, we propose to introduce experimental farms and pilot farms where appropriate management of SI-traceable sensors could be funded. This intermediate level could maintain the metrological link between metrological expertise and animal farming management expertise, through the verification of model trueness based on long-term monitoring studies. Animal farming management expertise is necessary to improve the description of animal production processes and identify the most relevant accompanying parameters for emission accuracy. This link could benefit from an international sectorial task group on animal production activities managed by BIPM in order to define taxonomies (Connor et al., 2024) and disseminate improvements in metrology or modelling (BIPM-OIML, 2021). The final level would include all other animals recorded in national inventories. These herds cannot be monitored intensively because of economic and environmental reasons. Estimates on landscape scale are necessary to assess the efficiency of long-term mitigation strategies. That's why we propose to verify and improve when necessary, the trueness of emission factors of all categories through the combination of bottom-up and top-down approaches. Bottom-up approaches can be based on emission factors and activity data. Emission decrease on landscape scale should induce an observable decrease in nitrogen footprint in areas with small herds. In areas with dominant animal production activities, the association of permanent sites with remote sensing estimates (cf. ICOS infrastructure) and landscape modelling of emissions and deposition could be used to assess emission decrease (digital twins, combining bottom-up and top-down estimates for model calibration and adaptation; Reis et al., 2026). In areas with combined activities and significant contribution of animal production, atmospheric composition monitored through satellites could be used to identify periods where animal contributions are dominant or negligible on the basis of multi-gas approaches and thereby assess the long-term trend (cf. 5-year UNFCCC reporting).

6.3.4 Farmers' management tool

To help farmers, farm advisors, agricultural companies and institutions to collaborate to achieve acceleration in mitigation strategies, we propose to adapt the simplified method because of its cost-effectiveness. This tool has been initially developed during the CCCFarming project as a screening tool and adapted to communicate results to the farmers participating in the project. Emission estimates have been verified against reference methods in LUKE farm and Agroscope and uncertainty analysis has been improved during quantiAGREMI project. Farm emission assessment are used to draw pictures showing whether the farm is contributing to the "high emission farms" or to the "low emission farms" of a population of farms (Figure 40). All emission measurements contribute to a frequency histogram showing the risk of high emissions or not. Histogram classes are chosen according to the variability observed in the population of farms and centered on the national average emission factor of the animal farms.

The first page displays the main characteristics of the farm. We observed during the CCCFarming project that emission categories were not explained by these characteristics in most cases.

To implement this kind of tool an agreement on methods and data sharing would be necessary. The role of the previous farm monitoring system and associated international standards is to provide confidence in measurement results and adequate expertise of people trained to implement the measurement and interpret the results on the basis of expertise in animal production and emission processes.

Figure 40. Illustration of the proposed farmers' management tool (by INRAE)

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Field measurements of gaseous emissions in livestock buildings: A new approach using mass balance to improve accuracy

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1- Context and objectives

Agriculture is a major contributor to global gaseous emissions: Greenhouse gases (GHGs) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) and ammonia (NH₃) which decreases air quality

95% of global emissions 10%

→ Assessing these major sources in livestock buildings is crucial in order for reliable emission reductions from these facilities, which are essential to drive effective mitigation strategies.

The present study involved calculating the following (see Approach below):

- Cumulative emissions and their uncertainties (to improve precision)
- Independent carbon mass balance, to improve measurement accuracy
- Adjusted gaseous emissions, which has improved measurement accuracy

2- Material and method

Analysis of the GestCO2 dataset: (Brittany, 2017; <https://doi.org/10.15454/FQO7VA>)

- Poultry house: mechanically ventilated
- Continuous and intermittent measurements performed by well-trained staff

Hourly measurements taken and cumulative emissions calculated for 32 days:

Heavy CO₂ emissions calculated from CO₂ concentrations

$$Q_{CO_2} = Q_{air} \times \rho_{air} \times \Delta C_{CO_2}$$

$$Q_{CO_2} = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{air,i} \times \rho_{air,i} \times \Delta C_{CO_2,i}$$

Cumulative CO₂ emissions calculated from CO₂ concentrations

Measurand

What about uncertainty?

3- Calculate emission uncertainties

Measuring uncertainty (GUM method):

$$u^*(Q_{CO_2}) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n M_{Q_{air,i}}^2 + M_{\rho_{air,i}}^2 + M_{C_{CO_2,in,i}}^2 + M_{C_{CO_2,out,i}}^2 + M_N^2}$$

Uncertainty of each term:

M _{Q_{air}}	M _{ρ_{air}}	M _{C_{CO₂,in}}	M _{C_{CO₂,out}}	M _N
25%	3%	5%	5%	0%

Uncertainty was due mainly to Q_{air} and gas concentrations (C_{CO₂,in} and C_{CO₂,out})

Approach to improve measurement accuracy

Concentrations (Box 2) → Emissions (Box 2) → Mass balance (Box 4) → Variables iterations (Box 5) → Adjusted emissions (Box 5)

Calculate uncertainty (Box 3) → Calculate uncertainties (Box 6)

4- Calculate the carbon mass balance to improve measurement accuracy

Carbon input: $C_{Total, Input} = C_{LW, Initial} + C_{Feed} + C_{Bedding} + C_{Heating}$

Carbon output: $C_{Total, Output} = C_{LW, Final} + C_{Death} + C_{Manure} + C_{CO_2, Heating} + C_{CO_2, LW}$

Carbon mass balance: $Q_{CO_2} = C_{Total, Input} - C_{Total, Output}$

Why carbon? The total masses of carbon input and output provide independent and traceable measurements of carbon losses.

5- Calculate adjusted CO₂ emissions

Cumulative CO₂ emission

Adjusted cumulative CO₂ emissions

Measurement accuracy

Iterations on physical variables

Adjusted emissions

6- Perspectives

- > Calculate adjusted NH₃ and N₂O emissions
- > Calculate uncertainties in adjusted emissions and carbon mass balance

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